

Quantifying hidden massive red galaxies at $z > 3$

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Understanding when and how galaxies assemble is essential to unveil the complete picture of galaxy formation and evolution across the history of the Universe. In the local Universe, the gigantic massive ellipticals are thought to represent one of the most mature stages of galaxy evolution. Those massive systems seem to have formed at early times and through violent and rapid processes [1, 2]. In the last decade, deep observations have also revealed a population of remarkably dense massive ($M_* > 10^{10-11} M_\odot$) quiescent galaxies at $z > 2-3$ [3, 4] whose progenitors formed the bulk of their stars in luminous starbursts at $z > 4$ [5, 6, 7]. The existence of massive evolved systems at $z > 3$ has been recently spectroscopically confirmed [8, 9, 10]. In this sense, analyzing and quantifying the number density of massive galaxies that were already in place at early epochs can help us understand when those systems first appeared and how did they evolve.

Unveiling a new population of galaxies

The most complete currently available catalogs (e.g., CANDELS or 3D-HST) are built from UV/optical selected samples, which are biased against massive red (dusty or evolved) systems. Consequently, they are missing a substantial population of IR-bright but optically faint sources that are not detected even in the deepest HST images.

With the goal of complementing the deepest NIR-selected catalogs available in GOODS (CANDELS & 3D-HST), we conducted a comprehensive search of this elusive massive population at $z > 3-4$, first presented in [11]. Specifically, we found 33 Balmer Break galaxies (BBGs, also referred to as optically faint or HST-dark galaxies) selected as Spitzer/IRAC bright ($[3.6] & [4.5] < 24.5$ mag), H -band dropouts ($H > 26.5$ mag). We note that the luminosity in the 3.6 and 4.5 μm IRAC bands is a robust and unbiased proxy of the total stellar mass.

The nature of massive (red) galaxies at $z > 3$

To better understand the nature of this new population, we analyze the optically faint BBGs by comparing them with a mass-limited ($M_* > 10^{10} M_\odot$ and $z > 3$) sample and a color-selected ($H - [3.6] > 2.5$ mag) sample extracted from the CANDELS catalogs published for these fields.

As BBGs can be considered a continuation of the color-selected sample (if the selection was based on IRAC instead of F160W), their derived mass ($M_* > 10^{10} M_\odot$) and redshift ($z > 3$) distribution help us demonstrate that our color cut (implied in the H -band dropouts) translates into a mass and redshift selection.

From the Spectral Energy Distribution (SED) modelling, we find a strong evidence that massive red galaxies at $z = 3-6$ span a diverse range in stellar population properties. In order to explore those different star formation modes, we classify BBGs, according to their location with respect to the main sequence of star forming galaxies (MS) into Starburst (18%), MS (48%) and subMS

Figure 1: Plot from [11] showing the rest-frame U-V vs. V-J colors for BBGs and the CANDELS color-selected comparison sample color-coded by star formation modes and sized by stellar mass. The upper boundary (black wedge) separates quiescent galaxies (top left) from star forming galaxies (SFGs, bottom). The black diagonal line denotes an additional criterion to separate blue (bSFG) from dusty (dSFG) star-forming galaxies.

(34%) galaxies (see Figure 1).

Subdividing BBGs by their rest-frame UVJ colors (Figure 1), we also find a wide variety of systems. While it is true that the vast majority ($\sim 80\%$) of this optically faint population do correspond to dusty star-forming galaxies (dSFGs), some of which might be hosting AGNs in their center, $\sim 10\%$ correspond to blue star-forming galaxies (bSFGs) and the rest to quiescent galaxies. Although a few recent studies have also revealed a non-negligible number of objects consistent with being either post-starburst or quiescent systems [e.g., 10, 12] at that epoch, only 3 of our BBGs lie within the quiescent wedge and 3 more BBGs have mass-weighted ages that are old enough ($t_m > 0.9$ Gyr, symbols enclosed by a black square in Figure 1) to be consistent with evolved galaxies.

The role of BBGs in galaxy evolution

The abundance of this hidden population of massive red high- z galaxies is particularly relevant in the high mass end of the galaxy stellar mass function. Indeed, BBGs account for 30-40% of the known galaxies with $M_* > 10^{11} M_\odot$ at $4 < z < 7$ (Figure 2). The derived number density ($\sim 10^{-5} \text{ Mpc}^{-3}$) of massive ($M_* > 10^{11} M_\odot$) galaxies in the early Universe is extremely challenging for the most advanced galaxy formation models and state-of-the-art hydrodynamical simulations such as EAGLE [13] or Illustris [14], which struggle to reproduce the formation

of galaxies with more than $10^{11}M_{\odot}$ in the first 2 Gyr of the Universe (Figure 2). In fact, our results point out that 1 of every 30 massive, ($M_{*}>10^{11}M_{\odot}$), galaxies in the local Universe was assembled in the first 1.5 Gyr after the Big Bang.

These discrepancies between models and observations, even though the reason is unclear, suggest that a major revision of the formation and evolutionary mechanisms that yield to the built-up of galaxies is required.

Figure 2: Evolution of the number density of massive ($M_{*}>10^{11}M_{\odot}$) galaxies with redshift (bottom axis) and the corresponding age of the Universe (top axis). The fraction of the local number density is also shown in the secondary vertical axis. The values inferred from the CANDELS sample and those including the BBGs are shown with empty and filled red stars respectively. The blue and green lines show the number density predicted by EAGLE and Illustris simulations.

Conclusions & outlook

We have presented the detection and analysis of a new population of previously unknown optically faint massive red galaxies and gathered a more complete sample of the general population of massive galaxies at $z>3$.

Although the existence of optically faint objects has been known for a decade [15, 16], only recently several studies, have provided evidence of their ubiquitous existence [11, 17, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 26].

As a consequence of their highly obscure nature, optically faint galaxies were initially thought to be classical sub-mm galaxies (SMGs, [24, 25, 26, 27]). However, as

demonstrated in [18], most of them are much fainter at $870\ \mu\text{m}$ (median $S_{870\ \mu\text{m}} \sim 1.6\ \text{mJy}$) than extreme starburst and SMGs. In addition, they do not represent a homogeneous population, but a variety of transitional evolutionary states instead [11] – see also Figure 1.

The existence of this numerous population of massive galaxies at high redshifts, which may correspond to the progenitors of the most massive local galaxies, represents a challenge for state-of-the-art simulations which fail to reproduce their number densities.

In order to properly constrain and improve galaxy formation models, accurately accounting for the tail of massive galaxies at $z>4$ becomes vital. The main source of uncertainty of the observationally derived number density and physical properties is the lack of spectroscopic confirmation of these sources. Given their extreme faintness in the optical/NIR regime ($H>26.5\ \text{mag}$), ground-based spectroscopy remains extremely challenging. In this sense, ALMA will be crucial to first confirm their redshift and then constrain the amount of dust and gas in these systems, as well as discriminating between dust-enshrouded star formation and obscured AGN activity. Imaging in near- and mid- infrared wavelengths together with spectroscopy from the JWST will be also essential to understand their nature and characterize their star formation histories.

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